

Businesses carried out worldwide have been influenced by the phenomenon of Globalization 4.0. has allowed us to make various changes in all aspects and activities of the human being in different countries where an essential interdependence of markets was reflected. However, they allow reflection on all economic activities. In the particular case of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), this phenomenon creates an uncertain environment and opens the opportunity to develop a competitive environment and identify challenges and opportunities. Many elements are considered incident factors caused by Globalization 4.0 that affect Mexican SMEs. This work shows what factors affect the economic aspects and how the cultural factor is significant; the challenge of teamwork, cooperation, unity, and management of existing resources is also considered. Although Mexico has an influential business culture, it is not implemented in these companies; some seem unaware of a situation limiting their participation in conducting international business and improving their global competitiveness. This article shows the results of qualitative research based on the grounded theory proposed by Glaser and Strauss in 1967; the results obtained show how it is necessary to develop cultural aspects so that SMEs can achieve development and permanence over time. Globalization 4.0 is a phenomenon that affects international companies and represents actions and strategies to have an advantage over other companies, but what happens with SMEs is different; these types of companies do not have economic resources, and globalization 4.0 becomes a disadvantage. In our study, 80 % of SMEs do not have a business culture and are not prepared for globalization 4.0, and we also found that time is wasted on bad practices in 35 % of Mexican SMEs; training was lacking in 32 % of educational cases

Keywords: Industry 4.0, industry companies, business implementation, SMEs, Globalization 4.0, economic activities, teamwork, cooperation and administration

UDC 654.024
DOI: 10.15587/1729-4061.2022.263580

IMPLEMENTATION OF BUSINESS CULTURE FOR MEXICAN SMES VERSUS GLOBALIZATION 4.0

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Received date 24.06.2022

Accepted date 19.08.2022

Published date 31.08.2022

How to Cite: Sandoval-Gomez, R. J., Alvarez-Cedillo, J. A., Sarabia-Alonso, M. T., Alvarez-Sanchez, T., Perez-Garcia, R., Gonzalez-Vasquez, A. (2022). Implementation of business culture for Mexican SMEs versus Globalization 4.0. Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies, 4 (13 (118)), 34–43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2022.263580>

1. Introduction

Today, globalization has been a shared-use concept for at least half a century and was linked to the growing interconnectedness between the different areas of our world; it has been driven by economic, political, cultural, and technological forces, which in some countries is very well defined and has been applied.

At the World Economic Forum in Davos in January 2018, the concept of Globalization 4.0 was given.

In Mexico, start-ups do not know their characteristics, and in recent decades they have seen dramatic changes in family life, including increases in dual-income households and single-parent families, as well as a more significant number of employed adults who also care for their children.

Elderly or sick relatives and migration to other countries have increased [1, 2].

The impact of Globalization 4.0 brought risks and opportunities to the Mexican market, such as increased competition, increased opportunities, and a temporarily small changing environment [2–5]. The main characteristics that mark the Mexican business culture in SMEs are personal relationships, loyalty, and operational hierarchy. In Mexico, unlike in other countries, the significant decisions in SMEs are made exclusively from management positions or by the company owner, and the employees are not involved [6–9]. In addition, the lack of a business culture that focuses on the characteristics of Globalization 4.0 means that this type of company does not can participate in international markets [10, 11].

Scientific research on this topic are relevant because given the rules of the markets governed by Globalization 4.0 and the limited information or training of this type of company owners, which is why they cannot aspire to compete in the large international markets.

The studies carried out on the subject will influence its results for its implementation and its declaration in public policy to make Mexican SMEs competitive in international markets.

Therefore, the studies that are shown allow to influence the modern Mexican society and will allow helping the permanence in time of this type of company. This investigation follows each of the steps defined for scientific investigations. Furthermore, its results are of scientific relevance.

2. Literature review and problem statement

In the initial analysis of this research, a hypothesis was formulated, if SMEs develop an organizational culture that is based on trust, communication, respect, teamwork, the quality of innovation [12], and the implementation of technological development and digital inclusion, they will be able to participate more efficiently in strengthening society and ensuring the durability of the company. Let's derive from the latest information that establish that the birth, development, and growth of Mexican companies throughout this century date back to the Porfirian era, where the appeasement of the country by the government was attracted mainly by foreign direct investment, which was interested in developing the areas of communication, transportation, mining, energy. Gradually and as more capital increased in a few hands as a product of the economic and social system of the beginning of the century, other industries such as cement, steel, textiles, and beer developed, and a clear trend of Globalization 1.0 [13].

However, it was not until World War II that international markets were opened to Mexican consumer goods regardless of their quality because the central international powers, which were at war, could not produce the necessary goods for the population and, at the same time, concentrate their efforts on war. In this period, Globalization 2.0 was born [14].

During this period, the new international governance with international institutions and agencies. Capitalism with markets guarantees efficiency and government of justice.

During the economic history of Mexico, in 1957, it increased its exports of the number of Mexican products to the United States by 77 %. However, at the same time, not only Mexico but all of Latin America imported products, which significantly increased Latin America's dependence on the United States. The foundations of Globalization 3.0 are established in Mexico [15].

It should be noted that agriculture took on an essential role in this protectionist agreement. Thus, the security and endowment plots, the intimate connection between the private party and the legislature, allowed Mexico to more than twice the size of its economy consistently from the treatment side onwards. Mexico had built a private industry almost suddenly in thirty years [16].

The extensive stretch during which they won insurance and sponsorships made colossal curves in the nation's economy [17]. This condition gradually strengthened state sup-

port in the economy by including the work of a friend who needed bankrupt companies. The development of cooperation and government activity in the economy was only one side of cash; the other was security, ownership, and "support" of organizations.

Insurance reached the level of partnering with the legislature and the private sector against outside speculation (to stay away from new contenders); What is more, it advocated that the administration allows some remote organizations to contribute without allowing buyers of those equivalent companies to do so (for example, it long allowed Kodak, but not Fuji), arguing that the challenge was not such an essential effect on so little publicity [18].

However, the businessman had a hostage showcase; despite being inadequate in terms of the impetus to emphasize improving the nature of its items, it also did not show enthusiasm for shipping its items and looking for different markets since then. Therefore, it was redundant as it had secure buyers.

That is why tariffs could not develop like imports, producing a deficit in the exchange balance since product transactions evolved at 3 %, while imports did so at 9 % per year. It to allow to cover this deficiency, Mexico depended on external credits, which caused the obligation of the nation, which in previous years was compensated by the equalization of administrations due to the income of the travel industry; However, this idea slowed its rate of increase due in large part to the taste that Mexicans produced to travel abroad and since their burning, in general, would be faster than that of visitors visiting Mexico [19].

Before the agreement, Mexican industry required radical changes. Hannu Piekkola said that the cordial relationship that had united the administration and the private party for a long time of shared objectives, trying to propagate the social circumstance that described the nation's economy during the previous decades is a trend [20].

The opening is given, despite the opposition of the vast majority of national entrepreneurs and even against the resistance of a good number of transnational corporations. The opposition to private enterprise is understandable if one considers the long years of protection and the absence of a strong export sector [21].

Likewise, opening our borders to all kinds of products indiscriminately only caused the fall in production and the closure of many companies, as imports were stimulated without regard to domestic products; In addition to this, the preference of the national consumer for different products.

Currently, under the influence of Globalization 4.0, where digital technology and the adaptation of digital processes, the international arbitration of wages is broken; without the physical movement of workers, there is also a revolution in the face of globalization in services [22]. Regarding communications, [23] mentions the importance of using networks to improve processes; within distribution processes, training and correct planning using intelligent algorithms are very important, and this added value impacts any Mexican SME.

The Mexican business sector is made up mainly of micro, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which determine a vital economic role in Mexico because they constitute 97 % of the Mexican economy, are thus the basis of our economy; and, without a doubt, the economy of any country due not only to its ability to create sources of work but also to low

capital requirements, low demands for foreign exchange and their technological flexibility.

Definitions of small and medium-sized enterprises differ in different countries. In Japan, for example, companies are classified by the number of employees and the amount of capital invested, while in the United States, companies are classified only by the number of employees.

In Mexico, following a decree published on December 3, 1993, in the Official Gazette of the Federation, SMEs are classified as follows:

1. Micro companies. There are those with more than 15 workers and have annual sales of less than 900 thousand Mexican pesos (MXN).

2. Small businesses. Are those between 16 and 100 workers with annual sales of less than 9 million Mexican pesos (MXN).

3. Medium-sized companies. Employ 101 and 250 workers with annual sales of less than 20 million Mexican pesos (MXN).

Although most Mexican companies are SMEs, this characteristic can present them with great opportunities since Globalization 4.0 does not necessarily imply that the big fish eats the child but that the most efficient displaces the inefficient. The support of digital technology and the Internet has allowed them to develop concrete digital strategies. Grande is not synonymous with efficient; sometimes, it means the opposite. A tactic of large companies to achieve greater productivity is to divide into SMEs.

Business experience clarifies that it is not always the big thing that leaves more profits. The tendency of the vast international monsters is, paradoxically, to divide into several companies with increasingly independent administrations, although communicated through advanced technology [22].

Large companies would like to continue to have all the benefits of their size without the drawbacks of bureaucratization. However, they have realized that to compete with small businesses with faster movements; these giants must behave like fast-moving small businesses. In other words, they must be recreated as a set of small, independent, and manageable units. Hence the importance of reengineering, reducing the size of organizations, outsourcing, and decentralization [24].

It is how the size of most Mexican companies becomes an advantage and an opportunity to compete in a world market, which requires fast movements and high adaptability.

The cultural factor is the main challenge. However, in addition, Mexican companies face their quest to increase their international competitiveness, which brings a series of challenges, to a national artistic nature, for Mexican companies [25].

Right or wrong, every company has a corporate culture; however, because this aspect is not considered in Mexican companies, it has been thought that our companies do not have a corporate culture; in reality, our organizations are not characterized by having a well-defined and elevated culture, but there are aspects that most companies share and take root within their organizations as part of a culture.

Most SMEs tend to develop a type of culture that is resistant to change, mainly because perhaps, that company was very successful in the past, and that fact starts with a visionary entrepreneur, someone who creates a highly successful strategy and who manages to obtain a relatively dominant position in some markets. That dominant position brings them more success and growth over time, which, if

not very careful, leads to various situations which ultimately create a culture resistant to change [26].

On the one hand, managers become increasingly arrogant because they consider themselves very good, so they stop listening, look inward and eventually centralize everything around them. On the other hand, however, that kind of culture anchors progress [27].

These cultural aspects that stand out most within Mexican companies; In addition to producing as much as possible, not as well as possible, which was adopted at one time, promoted a protectionist culture, which diminished or, in some cases, wholly eliminated competition between the various producers, who had a practically captive market.

If the final consumer thought that the prices or quality were unacceptable, it had no choice but to shut up and choose the cheapest or least lousy product. So, unfortunately, the consumer sometimes resorts to economies of scale, illegal importation, or smuggling.

Thus, our national and historical culture deeply affects Mexican business culture. However, in most respects, our culture is far from what would be the new global business culture, which seeks business leadership, a delegation of responsibilities, values within the organization that help promote teamwork, initiative, trust, and creativity; and above all that there is a high degree of motivation in all participants and levels of the organization. All of which will help the company adapt better and faster to the unexpected events and changes that are currently occurring [28].

For this reason, Mexican companies will find in each of these aspects to modify a challenge within their organizations, which will be significantly important, although it will not be easy to overcome.

The phenomenon of Globalization 4.0 has been presented lately and has had greater strength and, consequently, more significant repercussions. The first impact of Globalization 4.0 was to allow international companies to have an advantage over other companies that still had a national orientation. In the first phase of Globalization 4.0, it was globality itself that gave that advantage, that is, the ability of a company to mobilize its supplies and assets beyond borders; But now, anything a company can access remotely is no longer a competitive advantage because today everyone has access to it through the use of the Internet and new technologies [29].

The result is a common situation in which competitors are even a company must obtain supplies from the location with the lowest cost of placing production plants in nations of cheap labor. However, the companies that will win the markets will excel in managing their people and those with a culture within their organizations that allows them to adapt to unexpected changes and respond quickly.

Thus, in this highly competitive and changing world, the will to introduce new strategies and practices is an absolute necessity, and it is a reality that in many companies, the ties that prevent introducing these changes are cultural.

Resistance to change, apathy, or simple distrust can stagnate Mexican companies and allow competing companies to enter better conditions. Therefore, the need for change becomes frequent, and SMEs must recognize that "the only constant from now on will be changed" [24].

In Mexico, the alternative is to create a new business culture based on employee motivation, creativity, trust, loyalty, work, initiative, and enthusiasm, achieved by creating a pleasant and participatory work environment; then, respon-

sibilities are delegated. However, there are leaders across the organization who drive processes continuously; there are values that exalt employees, organization, and teamwork; so that people feel proud of where they work and let go of bureaucracy, apathy, and selfishness.

Implementing this culture could be more urgent in SMEs due to the importance and participation at the national level.

Different approaches to this problem have been addressed in the literature; for example, [30] showed the main objective to identify and analyze the strategies that some companies in Latin America and Europe implement to be competitive, and some success stories and characteristics found in Mexico were shown. In [31], The main results shown by these authors highlight that technological capacity significantly influences open innovation and eco-innovation practices and does not depend directly on business performance but through processes that stimulate open innovation or eco-innovation. In [32], this article shows the necessary bases for the development and implementation of organizational paradigms that provide specific solutions for SMEs to increase their productivity and competitiveness and strengthen their competitive advantages; however, they seek to streamline operations to adapt to the competitive environment, and they neglect human and interpersonal relationships. They consider the resource-based theory where five dimensions stand out (acquisition, use, coordination, functional efficiency, and managerial style. In [33], a study was carried out with a sample of 1,012 SMEs from the Northwest region of Mexico; all the data obtained were made from a structured survey addressed to the managers of the companies, and an analysis of variance was used through the Method of Structural Equations. The results indicate that dynamic capabilities strongly influence SMEs' entrepreneurial orientation, innovation, and profitability.

The unresolved scientific problem from the literature leads us to investigate whether Mexican SMEs can meet international standards that will lead them to compete in large international markets.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the study is to correctly implement the new international business culture in small and medium-sized Mexican companies to achieve their permanence over time and position themselves and consolidate accurately in Mexico. Furthermore, it allows them to enter global and international markets with high competitiveness using the norms of Globalization 4.0 and Society 5.0.

To achieve this aim, the following objectives were met:

- carry out qualitative research based on grounded theory, with which the main elements obtained by the coding will be determined;
- determine the characteristics of the culturally dominant organizational structure in the SMEs analyzed;
- substantiate the choice of leadership strategy.

4. Materials and methods

The problem posed for this research is to know the main elements that make up the organizational culture in SMEs

in Mexico. Therefore, this investigation was analyzed from the point of view of Globalization 4.0, as well as identifying this type of SME, its cultural strengths, and weaknesses.

This research was focused on determining the characteristics of the culture-dominant organizational structure in the analyzed SMEs. This paper shows the relevant aspects of creating a new business culture for these micro and medium enterprises by developing organizational structures that allow them to adapt quickly to change.

The new design will generate a new international philosophy and a new philosophy that will focus on reengineering production and maximization of profits. Likewise, it represents the first ties that allow the development of unique essences in Mexico mixed with cultural and educational aspects, education from the family, and are fed back and supported by society (Society 5.0).

Our discussion focuses on the theoretical model of [34], which different articles in the literature have addressed, and where the works converge in the improvement and development of competitive advantages, highlighting the methodologies to create, to maintain them.

The main idea related to the development of a business culture focuses on the development of business values, which include that employees feel made to feel in the organization, are motivated to be considered their ideas and contributions to the company, and in there is an environment of respect, trust, teamwork, development, and an internal structure that will generate an essential competitive advantage because the buyers and suppliers will automatically value the service attitude. And the atmosphere of cordiality in that organization [35].

In this paper, the hypothesis arises of the need for a research question: "If Mexican companies do not adopt a new culture focused on international business, they will be absorbed by others that do."

However, Mexico has yielded to economic openness and confrontation with foreign competitors; these implement very aggressive strategies of production, marketing, and promotion of goods and services in terms of leadership in quality management, process engineering, innovations, teamwork, inventory control, Internet and technology.

Qualitative research is any type of research that produces results and discoveries in which statistical procedures or other means of quantification are not used [36].

Qualitative analysis refers to rational and non-mathematical reinterpretation to discover keywords, concepts, and relationships in raw data and then organize them into a theoretical scheme [37]. These qualitative methods are used in particular substantive areas about which little or much is known, but new knowledge is sought [38].

There are three main components to qualitative research:

1. Data may come from different sources, such as interviews, observations, documents, records, and films.
 2. The procedures used to interpret and organize the data, such as:
 - a) conceptualize,
 - b) reduce data;
 - c) develop categories in terms of their properties and dimensions;
 - d) relate the data using a series of prepositional phrases.
- The above four points are known as coding.

3. Written and verbal reports can be presented as articles in scientific journals, talks (for example, in congresses), or books.

According to the purpose of this study, the methodology used for data analysis is the grounded theory proposed by [38, 39] and described by [40].

For [41], grounded theory is a research method in which theory arises from systematically collected data. It does not begin with a preconceived theory, but the theory will emerge to resemble reality from the data. Since the authors' purpose above was to create new ways of understanding reality and expressing it theoretically, the methods would help build theories. Given the above, grounded theory is the appropriate method for this study.

For this research, an in-depth interview was applied with 40 informants. For the analysis and coding of data, free software for qualitative analysis, Taguette, was used [42]. After performing the data analysis, the results were obtained and compared with the most relevant studies to detect trends.

Taguette stores the information in nodes, structured in hierarchies or trees, creating topologies to elaborate data analysis. According to the methodology used, we seek to find the elements that make up the keywords or properties and, with these, create the categories.

However, Taguette software uses the constant comparison technique; as the encoding is generated, the information found in a text is continuously compared with other encoded texts. The categories and properties that emerge from the analysis are combined with the sought vital concepts. It is possible to search for more data from the main keywords to strengthen the initial theory.

The software also shows when theoretical saturation has been reached, that is, the supersaturation of the analyzed elements and categories. It allows to focus the search on saturated items and search the documents for those nodes that have not yet reached that level. As per the information presented for this review, the word recurrence is displayed in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Word cloud created with Taguette software
Source: prepared based on a methodology

As should be visible in the examination of the word recurrence addressed in a cloud, it features the central matters identified and the essential component of the issue.

5. Results of research on implementation of business culture for Mexican SMEs versus Globalization 4.0

5.1. The qualitative research based on grounded theory.

A qualitative research was carried out where the following factors were found:

1. The SMEs do not adapt to changes in the environment.
2. The SMEs do not have a differentiating factor.
3. The SMEs do not have a long-term vision.
4. The SMEs do not have a business definition.
5. The SMEs do not have a transparent business model.
6. The SMEs do not create value, or it is not clearly shown.

Fig. 2 shows the percentage of frequency for each problem (200 samples).

Fig. 3 shows the main aspects that define the organizational culture.

As can be seen in the previous results obtained, it is observed that the interest in obtaining well-being in Mexican SMEs has constantly been changing; in recent years, the well-being of employees at the individual and organizational level is an essential factor to develop and is a need.

Fig. 2. Percentage of frequency for each problem (200 samples)
Source: Own elaboration

Fig. 3. Frequency for each element evaluated to know organizational culture (200 samples)
Source: Own elaboration

The data obtained in the analysis allows us to limit the term recultured organization.

A re-culturized organization is characterized not only by its organizational excellence, financial success, and excellence but also because it enjoys a physically and psychologically healthy workforce; this strength is capable of maintaining an optimal work environment and an authentic organizational culture and competitive for any globalized market waiting for social and economic changes.

This type of SME will be a healthy, competitive organization that preserves the organizational culture, work environment, and good practices, where safety is promoted individually and organizationally.

5.2. Characteristics of the culturally dominant organizational structure

Taking into account the problems presented in the section 5.1 and once the diagnosis has been made and using the Grounded Theory for the 200 samples analyzed and taking the organizational culture as an objective point, it is proposed as a solution to create strategies based on the Porter Positioning Model, applied to its three possible axes of knowledge to implement:

1. Cost leadership strategy.
2. Differentiation strategy.
3. Focus strategy.

Following the analytical process that Porter proposes in his model, which aims to keep the organization in a good position in the market and the proposal of strategies to protect that position [40, 41].

Others authors refers to the fact that competitive strategies establish the search for a prosperous competitive place in the sector where the organization is developed, and it is precisely in the sector where it is developed that competition appears [42]. When applying competitive strategies in the organization, it is possible to achieve and maintain an advantageous and reasonable position before the competition of the corresponding sector and it is necessary to implement the business culture.

5.3. Choice of leadership strategy

The advantages of the use of cost leadership strategy are the following:

1. Low costs allow low prices. Cost-leading companies focus on increasing production processes' efficiency to reduce production costs. As a result, low costs help SMEs lower prices while making a profit.

2. Companies can resist international price wars because they are prepared to reduce their costs, which can deter competition and is a critical differentiator. With these strategies, higher-priced competitors are less likely to face direct competition because they cannot guarantee they will win.

3. Companies can enjoy a more significant local and international market share. The company with the lowest prices will likely sell the most units, increasing its market share.

The disadvantages of the use of cost leadership strategy are the following:

1. The approach can be risky. Companies must constantly innovate, using new ways to reduce costs. In addition, competitors will likely copy the methods used when a company discovers an effective cost reduction method.

2. It cannot be easy to maintain perceptions of quality. It becomes problematic when marketing revolves around offer-

ing the cheapest products possible. Companies have to find a way to maintain a positive image and build brand loyalty.

3. Companies depend on a high sales volume because they will operate with reduced profit margins.

4. Companies may take time to adapt to market changes.

6. Discussion of results of the study of the implementation of business culture for Mexican SMEs versus Globalization 4.0

Around the world, SMEs study plans and strategies to make their growth. However, many of these efforts are of little use if, within the company, there is an atmosphere of apathy, distrust, insecurity, and general discontent [41, 42].

The new business culture allows for the immediate adaptation of new management practices, including process reengineering, total quality, just-in-time Japanese practice, and the gradual increase of its economy, technology, and the Internet.

The current international business environment is changing and temporary, so it is impossible to predict the position and state in which the company will find itself in the future [43].

However, globalization 4.0 and other fields have affected the business sector. How religious is the educational and organizational family, a political system that brings structural modifications, concept idea of many reference patterns, customs, habits of beliefs, family life, institutions and companies [44].

On the other hand, countries are looking for more participatory and democratic ways that foster economic and socio-ecological accountability and fight against everyday security problems, social degeneration, overpopulation, hunger and social inequality. In the information and technology sector, where knowledge is considered a source of maximum etiquette value for individual states, police changes are exponential. Millions of databases have been generated on information, different aspects and characteristics of the human being in which their data exploit their habits and customs.

Globalization 4.0 has been accentuated since the 1980s and in the early 1990s after the fall of the Berlin Wall and other events such as the disintegration of the former USSR, leaving the Cold War, the end of communism and different related ideologies for history. As a result, a third of humanity related to socialist or communist regimes saw the need to relocate within the capitalist world, and with this, a complex ideological change occurred [45].

The main advantage of Globalization 4.0 is that it is understood as a global process characterized and maintained by national economies that allows us to produce anything anywhere on Earth and sell it anywhere else [46]. The opening of borders was the economic mechanism that allowed the development of Globalization 4.0. Some countries implemented protectionism to try to block it; however, it is impossible to modify it by ignoring it [47]. The current scheme is almost impossible for a country. Triple protectionism sincerely affects a world economy to self-marginalization, and its possibility of development would be minimal in a modern world.

Globalization 4.0 has led to a phenomenon called globalization that is characterized by the economic opening of unequal competition where small, large companies destroy this phenomenon today in developing countries and is one

of the main risks of small and medium enterprises in Mexico due to their little control in other times due to their high corruption.

An important factor affecting SMEs is price standardization because they lack an economy of scale. It causes many companies to adopt the role of suppliers or subcontractors of large companies [48]. The proposed strategy for SMEs to make radical changes allows them to exist, and their growth focuses on generating value-added processes, implementing high-tech speed systems in decision-making and changing mentality.

Globalization 4.0 and competition do not leave it up to the natives to successfully improve the chances of SMEs to successfully overcome the challenges of a global community. International standards expect any product Made in Mexico to be as good as a product made in Germany, the United States or Japan; the service offered will have the same quality presented in any more developed country.

The change of attitude to maintain leadership in the market must meet and comply with quality standards in each production and marketing process. The environment where time is a factor where technology accelerates exponentially in front of the organization must have a proactive attitude to anticipate future and probable events, and this can only be done through a flexible structure. Companies with this new culture must be centralized and decentralized, while global and local ones have to make long-term plans and yet remain flexible.

It must develop flexibility as a constant, and competitiveness will end with pyramidal substitutions inherited from the military and ecclesiastical organization, thus generating a new type of organization called molecular organization. In a molecular organization, each unit or area of the company must have the autonomy to analyze the market is a specialty to make decisions freely and can adapt to changes quickly and safely from of all experience, however, as a dependent molecule intimately linked to the other molecules.

SMEs that do not implement this new culture will not be able to compete in an international global economy if they do not have high quality at low cost if they do not implement a culture of high trust, that is, self-confidence with supplier employees. In addition, in terms of motivational aspects, it is necessary to point out the new chalk business culture by employees who work at the same pace, which produces high levels of profitability, commitment and loyalty, which allows a low turnover of friendly or multipolar company personnel of family type.

Linked to motivation is creativity that does not arise from security. On the other hand, the security of these recognition jobs, shared values and behaviors with which people feel good when working in a company allows to enhance creativity by understanding all the processes, business models and typical activities of the company and contributing part of the knowledge of the company.

The Mexican business sector and its experience in the area of globalization 4.0 Mexican companies were affected since the 40s by a trade policy of total protectionism this state interventionism created completely biased incentive systems that directly undermined the competitiveness of companies, thus causing a lag in front of the outside world [49].

This lag is manifested when Mexico adopts a strategy opposed to protectionism, thus opening its doors indiscriminately to foreign trade. However, external conditions require

a free policy, nor can a deregulated market be justified as to which Mexican small and medium-sized enterprises were primarily exposed.

The results presented throughout this work establish the base to answer the research question. Based on the qualitative analysis, relevant aspects that influence the business culture were identified. The lack or scarce entrepreneurial culture in Mexican SMEs, and due to the lack of academic preparation of the owners or managers of this type of companies, it is shown that Mexican SMEs only have a useful life of 5 years or less, although there is a public policy in Mexico, it is applied to various government programs to support them. The reason for this may be that programs do not work well due to unresolved issues related to their operation, operation and logistics; however, all these factors are related to our object of study. Therefore, strategies were implemented to overcome these difficulties.

The results acquired are overwhelming:

1. 80 % of SMEs accepted that the entrepreneurial culture was insufficient.
2. Time optimization improved by up to 35 %.
3. Harmony between work and individual life improved by 35 %.
4. Harmony between nearby needs and market demands. International improved by 32 %.

5. Two of the SMEs in the sample have managed to enter international markets under the precepts of globalization 4.0.

Comparing the results in the literature [48] I only manage to obtain maximum results of 20 % in most of the items mentioned.

The advantages of the correct application of the business culture with a view to globalization 4.0 are:

- integration between the members of the organization, the owners and the collaborators;
- the members of the organization identify with the company, they feel part of it;
- SMEs get to be different from others given their value-added characteristics and allows them to integrate into the competition;
- increase motivation, members and collaborators feel accepted.

This research is limited to SMEs that have been able to survive the Covid-19 pandemic that are well defined and that their product or service is popular in Mexico.

The disadvantages of the correct application of the business culture with a view to globalization 4.0 are:

- it represents a barrier against change: when the environment undergoes rapid change, the organization's fortified culture would no longer be adequate and the organization would resist further modifications;
- it is a barrier to diversity: management seeks to make new employees accept the core cultural values of the organization so that differences that these employees are not accepted;
- culture intensifies organizational engagement and increases the consistency of employee behavior.

7. Conclusions

1. Mexican companies, mainly small and medium-sized enterprises, have faced many obstacles to getting ahead, and their foray into international business has been challenging.

However, they also present great opportunities, which will be very important to seize; simultaneously face and overcome the challenges presented to them to reach a high level within Globalization 4.0 and remain within global competitiveness. The new modern society (Society 5.0) has been affected by the inclusion of digital phenomena and the Internet, which directly affects SMEs, generates new products, modifies new tastes and consumer characteristics, and is reflected in Globalization 4.0, which produces a new international business culture. International standards expect any product made in Mexico to be as good as in another country. Therefore, to maintain leadership in the market, the change of attitude must meet quality standards.

Mexican SMEs need to give a new approach to their culture to face the challenges and opportunities presented by the environment successfully, to be displaced from international markets and maintain a good position in the national one, to create a pleasant and reliable work environment that involves employees, customers, suppliers, with the organization; feeling part of it to achieve its goals and be competitive in the current global climate.

2. This research showed that organizational culture is a significant factor for Mexican SMEs because it affects the exchange of knowledge and distances them from international markets. Other companies that show values such as competitiveness and competition focus on performance measures, which is not a correct evaluation parameter. Companies with cultures with collaborative characteristics, where people are encouraged to communicate and create a friendly and non-competitive atmosphere, are likely to share the values of the organizational culture. According to the findings of this research, different cultural values can lead to different patterns of knowledge sharing that strengthen SMEs in the face of Globalization 4.0. Consequently, this document emphasizes the need to know

the type of dominant culture as a determining factor of the different factors and styles of Mexican SMEs.

3. The generic strategies obtained in this research are essential because their implementation will be managed by executives who must maintain the competitiveness of their companies. This type of executive must identify the source of their company's competitive advantage, choosing how to compete in international markets by implementing low-cost strategies. They must focus their efforts on a globalized market. These SMEs will pursue cost leadership, differentiation, focused cost leadership, or differentiation strategies.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

Acknowledgments

We appreciate the facilities granted to carry out this work to the Instituto Politécnico Nacional through the Secretariat of Research and Postgraduate with the SIP: 20220233, 20220556, and 20221302 projects. Furthermore, to the Interdisciplinary Unit of Engineering and Social and Administrative Sciences, Center for Technological Innovation and Development in Computing and Digital Technologies Research and Development Center. Likewise, the Program of Stimulus to the Researchers' Performance (EDI) and the Program of Stimulus COFAA, PEDD, CONACYT, and Instituto Tecnológico Superior del Oriente del Estado de Hidalgo (ITESA).

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